

IMPLICATIONS OF BANDITRY ON HUMAN SECURITY IN KATSINA STATE, NIGERIA (2010-2024)

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Abstract

The North West region of Nigeria has been plagued by banditry for over a decade. This research paper investigates the impacts of banditry on human security in Katsina State, Nigeria, by exploring the complex sociocultural, economic, and environmental factors that exacerbate banditry, such as poverty, unemployment, drug abuse, environmental degradation, farmer-herder clashes, easy access to firearms and ammunition, and porous borders. Guided by the Human Security Theory and the Frustration-Aggression Theory, this research adopts a qualitative approach, utilising thematic analysis to provide a comprehensive understanding of the research phenomenon. The findings show that banditry activities such as cattle rustling and kidnapping for ransom affect human security in Katsina State by posing physical, economic, environmental, health, psychological, food, and political threats. Additionally, this paper analyses the effectiveness of policy responses such as community policing and vigilante groups. Through qualitative data from in-depth interviews, the paper brings into the limelight the struggles and perspectives of rural communities in the wake of the incessant attacks. As a result of the findings, the study suggests various recommendations, including strategies for advocating the improvement of the human condition, such as tightening border security, promoting modern ranching practices, awareness initiatives on drug abuse, creating employment opportunities, and equipping security operatives. The findings also emphasise the essence of multi-stakeholder collaboration and community efforts in addressing banditry and fostering sustainable development. In conclusion, this study aims to provide useful insights for policymakers, government officials, stakeholders, and researchers in formulating adequate policies towards enhanced security and resilience in Katsina State.

Keywords: Human Security, Banditry, Katsina State, SALWs

Introduction

On October 1, 1999, Nigeria transitioned from three decades of military rule to a democratic era, ushering in the Fourth Republic. Despite this transition, threats to fundamental human rights continue to pose significant challenges to individuals nationwide, undermining the basic tenets of democracy. The landscapes of Nigeria are dotted with complex security challenges such as non-state actors in the form of armed banditry in the North West, Boko Haram insurgency, Niger Delta militancy, human trafficking, and cultism, among others. Katsina State, the third largest state in the North-Western region, has become the focal point of a wave of violence manifesting in the form of armed banditry. Katsina and Zamfara States are the most affected by this menace, which includes rape, murder, kidnapping, cattle rustling, and the wilful destruction of property and lives (Audu & Adamu, 2021). The most affected areas include Kankara, Safana, Batsari, Sabuwa, Jibia, Faskari, Dan Musa, Dandume and Dutsin Ma. Farouk & Abdullahi (2022) assert that these areas share borders with Zamfara State and Niger Republic through dense forestation such as the Rugu, Jibia and Gurbin Baure forests. Furthermore, the authors contend that banditry and ransom-kidnapping have become profitable businesses for these criminals. According to Al Jazeera (2024), armed groups target commuters and rural people in the Northwest and North Central regions of Nigeria, which have seen the largest concentration of ransom kidnappings in recent years. The incapacity of security officials and local informants also facilitates this. Against this backdrop, there is a need for an academic inquiry into the origins, causes and human security implications of banditry in Katsina State.

Human security, as a concept, provides a comprehensive framework for examining the impact of banditry in Katsina State. It was first reported in the United Nations Development Programme Report (UNDP, 1994). Unlike traditional notions of security prioritising state sovereignty and territorial integrity, human security advocates protecting and empowering individuals and communities. According to the United Nations, human security is a people-centred, comprehensive, prevention-oriented notion of security that includes economic, food, health, environmental, personal, community, and political security, among other aspects that affect well-being. Human security must be promoted to create a compassionate society where people can live in safety and dignity, free from poverty, despair, and the dread of deprivation (Human Security Network, 1999). Human security is further divided by the United Nations into two categories: acute dangers, which arise from abrupt interruptions like natural disasters, and chronic threats, which include disease, poverty, famine, and conflicts.

Fundamentally, this study is a call to action since it aims to add to the expanding corpus of knowledge regarding the relationship between human security and banditry in Katsina State. It is also an appeal to academics, security agencies, and policymakers to acknowledge the human toll of banditry and prioritise the needs and goals of impacted communities. It is an appeal to respect each person's rights and dignity, invest in human security to achieve lasting peace, and address the underlying causes of violence rather than merely its symptoms. In the face of unimaginable adversity, the people of Katsina State have displayed extraordinary bravery and tenacity. By establishing an improved awareness of their strife and promoting solutions that bring optimism, security, and prosperity back into their lives, this research aims to honour their fight.

Methodology

The study adopts the qualitative method to provide a comprehensive and context-based understanding of the impacts of banditry on human security in Katsina State, Nigeria. The study focuses on the five most affected local government areas: Kankara, Jibia, Safana, Faskari, and Dutsin Ma, from 2010 to 2024. Data collection primarily

involves in-depth interviews with key stakeholders, including community members, security agents, community rulers and policymakers, to illustrate diverse viewpoints on the menace. A purposive or judgemental sampling technique is employed to ensure only those with relevant knowledge and information are interviewed. To find recurrent themes or patterns that illustrate the interviewees' first-hand experiences, the data is examined thematically.

Banditry in Katsina State

Katsina State, the Home of Hospitality, with a population density of 9.3 million and a landmass of 24,193 km, is located in Nigeria's Northwestern geopolitical zone. The present-day Katsina State was established on September 23, 1987, under General Ibrahim Badamasi Babangida's military rule. The Fulani Jihad of 1804, led by Sheikh Usman Dan Fodio, integrated Katsina into the Sokoto Caliphate, further entrenching Islam in its social and political systems. The Hausa Kingdom's fall led to the establishment of the Fulani Emirates. These were then divided into the Eastern and Western provinces. The Eastern province comprised Katsina, Kano, Bauchi, Yola, Gombe, Sokoto, and Zaria. During British colonialism, Katsina became part of Northern Nigeria's protectorate, with the Emirate system continuing under indirect rule.

Situated in the Sahel Savannah, Katsina State has a hot, semi-arid tropical savanna climate. It borders Niger Republic to the north, Kaduna State to the south, Kano and Jigawa States to the east, and Zamfara and Sokoto States to the west. The state's Northern and Western borders make it particularly vulnerable to banditry, as bandits from various states infiltrate Katsina to commit heinous crimes.

Banditry in Katsina State has become a persistent threat to human security, characterised by robberies, ransom kidnappings, cattle rustling, and attacks on local communities. Bandit warlords exploit ungoverned areas and forests within Katsina, such as the Rugu, Gurbin Baure and Dania forests, with rugged terrain serving as operational bases, launching violent raids that destabilise the local economy and displace populations. Over the years, banditry has evolved into an organised criminal enterprise, further complicating efforts to address the crisis. Bandits increasingly operate as networks with access to small arms and light weapons (SALW), allowing them to carry out more devastating attacks. It reached such an extent that the former Governor of Katsina State, Bello Aminu Masari, in 2019, declared that the state was under siege and had been overwhelmed by the bandits.

Banditry in Katsina State has its roots in long-standing socioeconomic and security issues. Historically, the region has experienced conflicts over land and resources due to desertification and population growth. These disputes intensified with the proliferation of small arms in the aftermath of Nigeria's civil war (1967-1970) and cross-border arms smuggling from neighbouring countries like Niger Republic. From the early 2000s, banditry evolved into a major security threat in Katsina, characterised by cattle rustling, kidnappings, and attacks on rural communities. Taking advantage of a weak state security presence and porous borders, armed banditry expanded from Zamfara State into the North-western states of Katsina, Kaduna Sokoto, and Kebbi, and Niger and Kogi in the North Central region in 2014. Armed banditry in Katsina State began in 2010 across seven LGAs: Kankara, Safana, Jibia, Batsari, Faskari, Dan Musa, and Sabuwa (Ladan & Matawalli, 2020). The widespread cattle rustling caused cattle scarcity in parts of Northern Nigeria, forcing herders to move their herds to safer regions further south. In 2016, bandits started depending more on kidnapping for ransom as a primary source of income due to declining livestock profits.

Katsina State Community Watch Corps (KSCWC)

Governor Dikko Radda established the Katsina State Community Watch Corps (KSCWC) in 2023 as part of his administration's community-oriented approach to support the efforts of security forces to fight against banditry in the state (Premium Times). The first batch, inaugurated in 2023, comprised 2,300 corps selected from across the 34 LGAs of the state. The Governor reinforced his commitment to fighting banditry, emphasising,

This should not surprise anyone, as 22 out of 34 local governments in Katsina face severe security challenges. A group of seasoned senior security professionals who had retired from various national security agencies was established before my inauguration. I also spoke with active security officers to learn more about the state's operational security architecture and the dynamics of insecurity (Vanguard, 2023).

In 2024, 550 personnel were chosen from ten LGAs, including Funtua, Danja, Kurfi, Matazu, Musawa, Bakori, Charanchi, Malumfashi, Kafur and Dutsinma, to form the second batch of the KSCWC. This increased the total number of corps to above 2000. In a fatal ambush in January 2025, 21 members of the KSCWC were killed in Baure village, Safana, while returning from paying condolences to the family of their deceased colleague (Al Jazeera, 2025).

Conceptual Review

Security

This is a state whereby people live in freedom from any danger or threat. Further definitions of security include: stability and continuity of livelihood (stable and steady income), predictability of daily life (knowing what to expect), protection from crime (feeling safe), and freedom from psychological harm (safety or protection from emotional stress, which results from the assurance or knowing that one is wanted, accepted, loved and protected in one's community or neighbourhood and by people around oneself (Nwanegbo & Odigbo, 2013). Security, according to Krause & Nye (1975), is the lack of immediate dangers to the minimally acceptable standards of the fundamental principles that individuals believe are essential for survival. Poku et al. (2007) state that contemporary security is linked to complex developmental challenges. Insecurity, on the other hand, refers to threats or disturbances eroding these core values, causing a decline in human safety, political cohesion and socioeconomic stability. Beland (2005) defines insecurity as a condition of worry or anxiety brought on by a real or perceived lack of protection. In North-Western Nigeria, insecurity manifests as armed banditry, which jeopardises both human security and socioeconomic security.

Human Security

Human security is a highly contested notion with no universally agreed-upon meaning. It seeks to shift the focus from traditional state-centric security to individual security. According to the United Nations (UN), human security entails people-centred, comprehensive, context-specific, and prevention-oriented responses that strengthen the protection and empowerment of all people. It comprises various factors influencing human well-being, including health, personal, economic, food, environmental, community, and political security. Such factors include violent conflicts, natural disasters, and epidemics. Human security was defined as "protection from chronic threats as hunger, disease, and repression, and safety from abrupt and hurtful disturbances in the structure of daily lives" is how human security was defined in the Human Development Report (HDR) of 1994. In conflict-ridden regions affected by banditry, insurgency and economic instability, the social fabric of communities is torn apart. This results in displacement, loss of lives, and pervasive insecurity. These conditions worsen poverty, fuel cycles of violence, and hinder development as affected populations struggle to meet basic needs. Furthermore,

such environments also create a breeding ground for the proliferation of small arms and light weapons, escalating criminal activities, and further destabilising the region.

Banditry

Banditry is a term used to describe organised crime in which a person or group of persons use means of violence or other threats to commit crimes such as armed robbery and kidnapping. In Nigerian societies, banditry is associated with property damage, murder, and maiming (Rufa, 2016). According to Brenner & Claire (2021), banditry is a form of organised crime that incorporates kidnapping, robbery, murder, rape, cattle rustling, and the misuse of natural resources. These crimes are committed with terror-inflicting equipment such as machetes, locally fabricated rifles, axes and or modern, sophisticated rifles and guns (Gabriel, 2020). Egwu (2016) further defines banditry as stealing cattle and animals from herds or raiding cattle from ranches with sophisticated arms. Rural banditry started as a struggle centred on resources and eventually developed into a regional conflict that took the form of rape, kidnapping, village attacks, and disputes between farmers and herders (Abdullahi, 2019). Bandits frequently operate in loosely organised networks, such as gangs, which may intersect with other criminal ventures. It poses a major security threat to democracy, socio-economic development and human security in North Western Nigeria, especially in Katsina, Kebbi, Kaduna, Zamfara, and Sokoto.

Cattle Rustling

This is the illegal theft of livestock, mainly cattle, and is often carried out by organised criminal factions for economic gain. It is primarily found in Nigeria's pastoral and rural regions, including the North-Western and North-Central areas. According to Cheserek et al. (2012) and Okoli & Okpaleke (2014), cattle rustling was defined as the unlawful and violent taking of livestock from their owners or communities using whatever weapon at hand, disregarding the loss of life and property of the victims. Cattle rustling in these regions is made easy by the proliferation of small arms and light weapons. It tampers with the livelihood of ranchers, causing huge economic losses, mass displacement and heightened insecurity.

Kidnapping

It occurs when an individual is taken against their will. Kidnapping in Katsina State is a lucrative criminal enterprise typically done for ransom or political motives. Stringent circumstances, such as poverty and unemployment, may push individuals into illegal activities, such as kidnapping for ransom, and they can severely harm or murder the victim if the ransom is not paid. Given that it exacerbates socio-economic disturbances and infringes upon people's fundamental human rights, this is arguably one of the greatest threats to human security. However, with the emergence of organised criminal groups and terrorists, such as Boko Haram, the bandits, and then the Fulani herdsmen, this scenario further deteriorated. Together, these groups took the issue of kidnapping in Nigeria to another level, approach and height, much of which was never known in the country (Odoemene, 2024)

Insurgency

Insurgency, or guerrilla warfare, is a direct, organised, and violent uprising against a state, government or other authority. It is typically perpetrated by non-state actors (NSAs), such as bandits or terrorists, aiming to overthrow or destabilise the state's established political or power structures. Additionally, they depend on the local communities for support, shelter and resources. Insurgents and armed forces usually have an asymmetrical relationship. The larger, better-equipped military faces the militants, who have fewer weapons. Armed insurgencies usually acquire weapons in four main ways. They begin with readily available weapons, then move to the previous leftovers, into stealing from the government, and lastly, acquisition from international sources,

including black market transfers (Jackson, 2010). Charles Cheney Hyde, an American attorney and expert on international law, claims a “rebellion” occurs when the government quickly suppresses a hostile group. However, the conflict between the two factions would be considered the equivalent of war under international law if the insurgents posed a significant threat to the government and were officially recognised as “belligerents”. Some instances of insurgents include Boko Haram, the Movement for the Emancipation of the Niger Delta (MEND), the Islamic State of the Levant (ISIL), Al-Shabaab, Janjaweed, Houthi Rebels, Tuaregs and the Taliban. These groups are motivated by political, religious, ethnic, cultural or economic considerations.

Small Arms and Light Weapons (SALW)

These are compact, portable and easily transportable weapons used by individuals and groups. Small arms are weapons designed for individual use, such as rifles, submachine guns, shotguns, carbines, revolvers, pistols and assault rifles. Light weapons, or Man-Portable Air Defence Systems (MANPADS), on the other hand, refer to ammunition designed for use by a small faction, and they include machine guns, grenade launchers, portable anti-aircraft guns, howitzers, rocket launchers, landmines, mortars and anti-tank launchers. While the SALW alone cannot start a fight, rebels' use of it has wreaked havoc and destroyed lives worldwide (Chelule 2014). In Nigeria, West Africa, and other parts of Africa, the proliferation of SALW is of significant concern due to its role in exacerbating regional conflicts, including armed banditry, insurgency (i.e., Boko Haram), militancy (i.e., Niger Delta militancy) and intercommunal clashes. These small arms and light weapons are either illegally trafficked across porous borders, remnants from previous conflicts (like the Libyan conflict or the Biafran War), or stolen from state armouries.

Empirical Review

Shehu et al. (2017), in their article titled “The Menace of Cattle Rustling and Banditry in North-West Nigeria: A Case Study of Katsina State”, investigate the prevalent threat of cattle rustling and banditry in North-West Nigeria, with a specific focus on Katsina State. It further highlights their detrimental impacts on economic stability, public safety and local well-being. The work reveals that these elements have wreaked widespread loss of lives, great displacement of people and major economic disruptions for pastoral communities due to cattle rustling. Key findings point to factors such as poor implementation of the Land Use Act of 1978, recurrent droughts and famine, struggle for grazing land, and resource agitation between farmers and herders. Additionally, the erosion of cohesion within the Fulani communities exacerbates the crisis. To solve these problems, the authors recommend maintaining conflict resolution through dialogue, constructing grazing reserves, and delineating stock routes. These aim to mitigate tensions, improve resource control and foster peace and unity between farmers and herders. In their study "The impact of armed banditry and kidnapping on socio-economic activities: a case study of selected LGAS in Katsina State, Nigeria," Farouk & Abdullahi (2022) used structured questionnaires in six local government areas and a quantitative research approach to assess the effects of these crimes on socio-economic activities in Katsina State. The findings indicated that banditry has drastic implications on poverty, unemployment, food security, education, health, income and the standard of living of the residents of the state. Hence, they recommended border security patrol units to curb the proliferation of arms and ammunition due to porous borders. Notably, they recommended tactical measures from security agencies to safeguard lives and property. They also suggested expanding the Universal Basic Education programs to accommodate Fulani herdsmen and to set up skill acquisition centres for the Fulani communities. The authors equally stressed the need to establish Fulani settlements, equipped with all the necessary amenities, in the unregulated forests. Lastly, they called for the guarantee of food security by providing adequate farming inputs to revive agricultural production.

The study "Banditry and the Complicity of Authorities in Zamfara State" by Mahmud & Maigari (2024) explores the causes and consequences of banditry in Zamfara State, emphasising the drastic implications of the crime on political governance, socio-economic stability, and human security. Utilising a qualitative approach based on the Human Security Theory, the research pinpoints the main causes of banditry, such as poverty, farmer-herder clashes, and the complicity of traditional and state authorities. The findings reveal that banditry has led to significant declines in economic stability, agricultural productivity, loss of lives and property, and political fragility, undermining governance and threatening democracy. Moreover, human security has been severely compromised, with human rights violations, widespread displacement, and the disruption of essential services in education and healthcare. The writers recommend integrated security strategies, community-based programs, economic development initiatives, enhanced government accountability, and conflict resolution mechanisms to mitigate the adverse effects of banditry and restore stability in Zamfara State.

Olopeju & Adeniyi (2022), in their study titled "The impact of banditry on Nigerian security in the Fourth Republic: an evaluation of Nigeria's Northwest", evaluate the alarming rise of banditry on Nigeria's security, emphasising the Northwestern region during the Fourth Republic. The paper adopted the Queer Ladder Theory (QLT) and the Frustration-Aggression Theory to identify the root causes of banditry, including poverty, mass unemployment, poorly governed spaces, porous borders, weak security agencies, and proliferation of arms. These factors have worsened issues such as loss of lives and property, cattle rustling, mass displacement, kidnappings and socioeconomic issues, forcing people into insecurity and fear. Additionally, the findings indicated that the efforts of stakeholders had yielded few benefits. The authors, therefore, recommended tactical governmental strategies, including creating employment opportunities to address poverty, tightening border security to curb illegal arms trade and illegal migration, and implementing rural reorientation initiatives to instil moral principles and human rights awareness. These efforts would enhance security, promote stability and foster sustainable development.

Theoretical Framework: Human Security Theory

Human security theory emerged in the late 20th century as a response to the limitations of traditional, state-centric security paradigms. The framework was first articulated in the 1994 United Nations Development Programme (UNDP) Human Development Report. Spearheaded by Pakistani economist Mahbub ul-Haq and supported by Indian economist and Nobel laureate Amartya Sen, the concept aimed to shift the focus from protecting states to safeguarding individuals and communities. By emphasising "freedom from fear," "freedom from want," and "freedom to live in dignity," this people-centric approach to security draws attention to how interwoven the security problems are.

In Katsina State, Nigeria, human security theory offers a robust framework for analysing and addressing the multifaceted challenges posed by banditry. By focusing on the well-being and safety of individuals and communities, human security provides actionable insights into the root causes and broader implications of banditry while guiding the development of holistic solutions. The 1994 report emphasised seven fundamental components of human security: food security, economic security, health security, environmental security, personal security, communal or community security and political security.

Conclusion

The impact of banditry on human security in Katsina State has surmounted mere statistics, rather, it is a horrid reality families must deal with, as their loved ones are murdered, displaced from their homes and farms, and their dreams snatched from their grasp. Human security transcends the absence of violence. It is the presence of dignity, hope and freedom to live without fear. However, the unrelenting vice of banditry overshadows these, making

them seem like a utopia to thousands in Katsina State. Agriculture, the region's main source of income, has been severely damaged, making it impossible for many people to make a living. Beyond the physical implications, ongoing pain and anxiety have taken a psychological toll that has damaged society and increased mistrust of government institutions and security forces.

Recommendations

The Katsina State Government should introduce safety net programs, unemployment benefits and loans for small and medium enterprises (SMES), among others, to reduce the socio-economic motives of banditry. Providing alternate, legitimate avenues of wealth creation can deter individuals from committing crimes. Furthermore, tightening border security, especially along the Nigeria-Niger Republic border, and deploying more security operatives to mitigate the crisis, along with sophisticated surveillance technologies to restrict the free movement of bandits and illegal arms. The state government, in collaboration with the NCCSALW, must implement stringent measures to curb the proliferation of small arms and light weapons. Policies should be aimed at disarmament initiatives and stricter firearm regulations to prevent SALW from falling into the hands of non-state actors such as bandits. Collaborations with regional bodies such as ECOWAS and neighbouring countries, including Niger Republic, to mitigate arms trafficking networks and share intelligence on their movements. Rehabilitation and sensitisation programs should also be created for youth. Lastly, there should be a transition to modernised ranching systems and the prohibition of open grazing.

Since banditry undermines various aspects of human security, a multisectoral approach is needed. Firstly, the state government should increase expenditure in agricultural activities to support farmers and restore livelihoods displaced by banditry attacks. Next, the healthcare sector needs restoration by investment in hospitals, emergency services and trauma counselling for victims should be done, to help with psychological trauma. Thirdly, community dialogue, support for local inclusivity should be done to rebuild trust and foster social cohesion. Finally, sustainable land use policies should be implemented, alongside promoting modernised agricultural practices.

In conclusion, interagency collaboration among Nigeria's security agencies will build a vibrant intelligence-sharing and support network to facilitate the speedy identification and mitigation of national security threats, improving response effectiveness. Lastly, civil-military relations should be improved to strengthen trust between local communities and security agents.

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